

TYPES AND DELIVERY METHODS OF FINANCIAL PRODUCTS OFFERED BY INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

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Financial products provided by international financial organizations are distinguished by their optimal and long-term nature in the architecture of the international financial system.

In the process of globalization of the world economy and transformation of national economies, a thorough study of the essence of financial products offered by international financial institutions is of great importance for member countries in their use, as well as in making informed decisions.

As you know, a financial product is a set of interconnected financial services, financial instruments, and technologies offered as commodities by international financial institutions in the international financial market [1]. A common similarity between international financial institutions is that the financial product provided is financed for specific purposes (programs and projects).

As we know, the World Bank Group is an international financial institution that provides major financial instruments and advisory services. This international financial institution allocates its financial resources through the following three financial instruments:[2]

- 1) financing of investment projects (financing of projects implemented within various sectors of the economy);
- 2) a lending program tied to the results of the project (allocation of credit resources depending on the results achieved within the project);
- 3) financing of structural changes and development goals of the country (allocation of financial resources to support institutional, structural, political, economic reforms in the country).

Since the main lending institutions of the World Bank Group are the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD) and the International Development Association (IDA), it is appropriate to analyze the financial products of these organizations. The IDB offers flexible and affordable financial products to its member countries to obtain resources. The IDA, on the other hand, provides loans and grants to poor, developing countries with very low or zero interest rates for 30-40 years.[3] In addition to the above, the World

Bank Group also offers guarantees, project preparation fund products, and special trust fund loans.

In the scientific works of E.A. Markelova, the financial products of the IBRD are divided into two groups: [4] 1) investment (flexible credit programs, loans for education and innovation); 2) systemic (credit programs for systemic reforms, special loans for sectoral systemic reforms) were analyzed separately.

V.V. Konovalov noted that the IBRD's systemic loans are provided for a period of 2-3 years for systemic reform programs, and among them, special loans have been formed for new systemic reforms.[5]

The World Bank Group classifies the economies of the world into four income groups: high-income, upper-middle-income, lower-middle-income, and low-income countries. Income is calculated as gross national income (GNI) per capita in current U.S. dollars using the Atlas method (see Appendix 5). This classification is updated annually on July 1[6].

The World Bank Group classifies member countries according to three criteria: regions, income levels, and financing groups. Within the regional classification, the Republic of Uzbekistan belongs to the Europe and Central Asia region; in terms of income, it is categorized as a lower-middle-income economy; and within the financing classification, it is placed in the blend group, meaning that it can access credit resources from both the International Development Association (IDA) and the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD).[7]

From this perspective, after the World Bank Group classifies member countries according to their level of economic development, it develops and offers the terms of financial products (such as loan interest rates, loan periods, and other conditions) that match each group's repayment capacity.

According to G. N. Ratnikov, in order for international financial institutions to mobilize more assistance and resources for developing countries, it is necessary to develop new directions and instruments.[8]

At the same time, scholarly works note that in the activities of international financial institutions, priority should be given to addressing problems in the national economy, eliminating crisis processes in a short period of time, and reducing their costs.[9]. This also implies the need for international financial institutions to review their financial products. Furthermore, the systematization of international finance and credit has been analyzed as important for developing concepts, financial policies, and identifying stability factors for

countries. This is explained by the fact that it can be used as an element of the financial product mechanism of international financial institutions.

The Asian Development Bank (ADB) also provides various financial products to its member countries, such as loans, grants, technical assistance, guarantees, and debt management products. It should be noted that the ADB finances its financial products through Ordinary Capital Resources (OCR), the Asian Development Fund (ADF), and special and trust funds. The financial products offered by the ADB include the following:[10]:

Local currency loans (LCL) – In 2005, a product in national currency was introduced to meet borrowers' financial needs. It is available to private sector enterprises and certain public sector entities. This financial product was developed to prevent currency mismatches in the country and to support the development of the local capital market. In addition, borrowers are allowed to change interest rates based on mutual agreements.

Concessional OCR loans (COL) – These are concessional loans offered at low interest rates aimed at narrowing the development gap in the Asia-Pacific region and reducing poverty in member countries. Concessional assistance to developing member countries is intended to help them overcome challenges in their development process and to promote inclusive and sustainable growth.

Debt management products – The ADB offers debt management products to its members to help manage obligations to third parties. By providing such products, member countries can improve the management of their external debt systems. Debt management products include currency swaps, local currency swaps, and interest rate swaps.

Furthermore, as noted in the scientific work of A. V. Shelepov, the ADB implements joint projects through co-financing (official, commercial, and other) and syndicated financing instruments [10].

The eligibility of developing member countries of the ADB to receive concessional financial resources is determined by two indicators:

- Gross national income (GNI) per capita; and
- Creditworthiness for ordinary capital resources, i.e., repayment capacity.

Similar to the World Bank Group, the ADB calculates GNI per capita using the Atlas method. The repayment capacity of member countries—that is, their ability to return financial resources—is classified into three categories: fully creditworthy, limited creditworthy, and non-creditworthy countries. From this

perspective, based on the above data, the ADB classifies its member countries under a three-tier system:

- Group A – eligible only for concessional assistance,
- Group B – eligible for both ordinary capital resources and concessional assistance, and
- Group C – eligible only for ordinary capital resources.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is classified by the ADB in Group B, meaning that the country is eligible to access both ordinary capital resources and concessional assistance.[11]

It is important that the above-mentioned international financial institutions implement their regulatory documents on the organization of financial product forms and distribution aspects in accordance with international standards. [12]. However, the establishment and recognition of international standards is only a condition and tool that creates the necessary prerequisites for strengthening the financial system and provides additional opportunities for economic growth.

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